

**17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference
including
Best of WCLC 2018**

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Dear colleagues,

It is our pleasure to welcome you to the 17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference including Best of WCLC 2018. The Conference is organized by Institute for Pulmonary Diseases in Sremska Kamenica and Central European Lung Cancer Association – CELCA.

The aim of CELCC is to develop strategies for decreasing the burden of lung cancer in Europe. Therefore, we invite different specialists working in the field of lung cancer to participate at the CELCC 2018.

Thank you for your highly appreciated contribution to this Conference.

We wish you a pleasant and rewarding stay in Novi Sad!

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, sincerely,

Prof. Dr Ilija Andrijević
Conference President

Prof. Dr Nevena Secen
Conference President

Prof. Dr Robert Pirker
Member of the Board CELCA

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SCLEROSING PNEUMOCYTOMA: OUR TEN-YEAR EXPERIENCE

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Introduction: Sclerosing pneumocytoma represents a rare, benign tumor of the lung with uncertain histogenesis and challenging diagnosis.

Goal: The goal of this study is to analyze demographic, clinical, morphological, histological and immunohistochemical features of sclerosing pneumocytoma.

Methods: This is a retrospective study of six patients diagnosed with sclerosing pneumocytoma in the ten-year period at the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina. The study analyzed various parameters that are: sex, age, symptoms, size and location of the tumor and its gross and histological features.

Results: Sclerosing pneumocytoma was more frequently diagnosed in females (83%). The patients ranged in age from 38 to 61. Most of the patients (66%) were asymptomatic. Two patients underwent a video assisted thoracoscopic surgery, 2 patients had a video assisted minithoracotomy, and 2 patients underwent a thoracotomy in order to remove the tumor. In 50% of the patients the tumor was localized in the lower left lobe, in 33% it was localized in the upper right lobe, and in the 16.6% the location was in the lower right lobe. The tumor size ranged from 1 cm to 2.5 cm. Pathological examination of all 6 cases reported that all 4 major histological patterns were found in tissue sections: solid, papillary, sclerosing and hemorrhagic. In all 6 cases, immunohistochemical analysis showed positive expression of TTF-1 and panCK in surface epithelial cells, and TTF-1 positivity and panCK negativity in round stromal cells.

Conclusion: Due to similarity with lung adenocarcinoma, adequate diagnosis of sclerosing pneumocytoma requires histopathological analysis with applying of immunohistochemical methods.

Keywords: sclerosing pneumocytoma; histopathology; immunohistochemistry.